

S1 (A) *Aurinia saxatilis* (L.) DESV.

S1 (B) *Barbarea vulgaris* W.T.AITON

S1 (C) *Brassica oleracea* convar. *capitata*

(a) var. *rubra* L. cv. Schwarzkopf

□ MS
▣ DMSO
▤ 0.03 mM progesterone
■ 0.03 mM testosterone

S1 (G)

Eruca vesicaria
subsp. *sativa* (L.) CAV.

(a)

S1 (H)

Erysimum cheiri (L.) CRANTZ

S1 (I)***Erysimum crepidifolium* RCHB.**

S1 (M) (a) *Lobularia maritima* (L.) DESV.
cv. Schneeteppich

S1 (N)
(a) *Malcolmia maritima* (L.) W.T. AITON

S1 (O) (a) *Matthiola incana* (L.) W.T.AITON

S1 (Q) *Raphanus sativus* var. *sativus* L. cv. *Riesenbutter*

S1 (R)*Sinapsis alba* L.**(a)**

SI Figure S2: Seedling and root morphology of progesterone- or testosterone-treated *Brassicaceae* species. The figure depicts the morphology of seedlings and roots of the following *Brassicaceae* species: (A) *Aurinia saxatilis* (L.) DESV. (B) *Barbarea vulgaris* W.T.Aiton, (C) *Brassica oleracea* convar. *capitata* var. *rubra* L. cv. Schwarzkopf, (D) *Camelina sativa* (L.) CRANTZ (E) *Cochlearia officinalis* L., (F) *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* (L.) DC., (G) *Eruca vesicaria* subsp. *sativa* (L.) CAV., (H) *Erysimum cheiri* (L.) CRANTZ, (I) *Erysimum crepidifolium* RCHB., (J) *Hesperis matronalis* L., (K) *Isatis tinctoria* L., (L) *Lepidium sativum* L., (M) *Lobularia maritima* (L.) DESV. cv. Schneeteppich, (N) *Malcolmia maritima* (L.) W.T. Aiton, (O) *Matthiola incana* (L.) W.T.AITON, (P) *Nasturtium officinale* W.T.AITON, (Q) *Raphanus sativus* var. *sativus* L. cv. Riesenbutter, (R) *Sinapsis alba* L., (S) *Sisymbrium officinale* (L.) SCOP. (a) gives the root lengths of the analysed plant as mean \pm SEM. Statistical differences, indicated by asterisks (* = $p \leq 0.05$; ** = $p \leq 0.01$; *** = $p \leq 0.001$), were determined by one-way ANOVA and Turkey test. (b – e) are pictures of the morphology of the seedlings. (f – h) show microscopic pictures of the root tips of the analysed plant. b and f = MS control; c and g = DMSO mock treatment; d and h = 30 μ M progesterone; e and h = 30 μ M testosterone. Green arrows indicate uncoordinated cell growth, while white arrows indicate enhanced root hair development.